

Sensitized photo-oxidation of osazone by uranyl ions

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Manuscript received 11 June 2002, revised 10 March 2004, accepted 6 April 2004

Glucosazone quenches excited uranyl ions, which involves excited state charge transfer complex (exciplex) formation. The quenching behaviour shows pH dependence. At pH 2.00, glucosone has been characterized as the photoproduct and intermediacy of uranium(V) is proved spectrophotometrically. A mechanism has been proposed.

Organic compounds possessing $>C=N$ are very useful¹. Uranyl ion is supposed to be present in natural water as uranyl carbonato complexes². It may photochemically degrade the pollutants and chemicals reaching through effluents in the presence of sunlight³. So photochemical degradation of these compounds will give an insight in environmental phenomenon. Sensitized photo-oxidation of osazone by singlet oxygen has been reported by Vaidya⁴. Reactions of osazone with uranyl ions will be of biological interest as it is biologically active compound and there is a lack of information on its photochemical behaviour⁵. It is therefore, decided to investigate the photochemistry of simple organonitrogen, compound glucosazone.

Results and discussion

On the basis of the analytical, chemical and spectral data, the main photoproduct was characterized as glucosone. IR data show the presence of CHO group (two moderately intense bands, one at 2825, 2717 cm^{-1} and other at 1389 cm^{-1} and $>C=O$ group (1720 cm^{-1}) in the photo-product. There is no absorption in the region 1470–1690 cm^{-1} , confirming the absence of $>C=N$ group in the photo-product⁶. The structure is further confirmed by quantitative elemental analysis of the photoproduct.

When solution containing uranyl ions U^{VI} and glucosazone were irradiated, the absorbance decreased and uranium(IV) was produced through intermediate U^{V} . Uranium(V) species were found as a consequence of the photochemical electron transfer from the glucosazone to uranyl ion and that the subsequent thermal disproportionation of intermediate uranium(V) to uranium(IV) and uranium(VI) occurs. The intermediacy of U^{V} was proved spectrophotometrically as depicted in Fig. 1.

U^{VI} absorbs strongly at 420 nm. U^{IV} absorbs at 550 nm and 642 nm. The absorption at 660 nm is assigned to U^{V} .

Fig. 1. Changes of uranyl ions with time (to prove intermediacy of U^{V} and (i), (ii), (iii) are reactions of Scheme 1); $\text{U}^{\text{VI}} = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}] = 0.024 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.006 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Light}] = 3 \times 200 \text{ W (tungsten)}$.

U^{V} is very unstable in aqueous medium at pH 2.0, and it disproportionate to U^{IV} and U^{VI} . At higher pH (2.0–4.0), its presence can be seen spectrophotometrically in non-aqueous medium. Same reaction was also carried out at pH 2.5 in dry acetone medium with perchloric acid. This solution shows a significant absorption at 660 nm after 2 h of irradiation⁷.

On the basis of experimental results, a mechanism of the photooxidation of glucosazone by uranyl ions has been proposed in Scheme 1.

The excited uranyl ions take electrons from the glucosazone (Q), giving exciplex. The charge transfer complex between excited state uranyl ions and substrate glucosazone i.e. exciplex ($\text{Sub}^+ \dots \dots 2\text{UO}_2^+$) is formed first, an electron is transferred from substrate to UO_2^+ changing U^{VI} to U^{V} . This exciplex is unstable in acidic medium and immediately breaks into glucosone (P), *N*-nitrosoaniline (R) and UO_2^{2+} . *N*-Nitrosoaniline is oxidized to *N*-nitroaniline

(S) (other product) by O^2 or uranyl ions. UO_2^{2+} so produced reacts with oxygen to yield UO_2^{2+} in presence of light.

where

Scheme 1. Sensitized photo-oxidation of glucosazone to glucosone by uranyl ions.

Experimental

Photo-oxidation was carried out in borosil glasswares exposed to 3×200 W tungsten lamp and oxygen was passed through the solution at the rate of $2.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. TLC was carried out using silica gel G (Merck) and freshly distilled solvents. Iodine (resublimised) was used to develop the spots. pH was measured on a Systronics-335 pH meter. Electronic spectra were taken on a Systronics-106 (Mk-II) spectrophotometer and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Grating - 377 spectrophotometer.

Glucosazone (synthesized and recrystallized, m.p. 205°) was used. Uranyl acetate (B.D.H.) and perchloric acid 60% (Merck) were used as such. Double-distilled methanol (B.D.H.) and acetone (B.D.H., dried over anhyd. calcium chloride) were used to prepare the solutions.

Procedure :

Glucosazone in methanol, uranyl acetate and perchloric acid were added and total volume of reaction mixture was made 100 ml by adding double-distilled water. The concentration of these ingredients in the reaction mixture was

glucosazone = $0.024 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, uranyl acetate = $0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, perchloric acid = $0.006 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (pH = 2.0). The solution was exposed to light source and oxygen was bubbled continuously by stirring. The steady state concentration of uranyl ions are maintained by conversion of UO_2^{2+} to UO_2^{2+} . The progress of the reaction was followed by regular TLC analysis at every 2 h interval. After 6 h of irradiation two spots were observed on TLC plate, one corresponding to parent substrate and the other to the photoproduct. The reaction was allowed to go for completion (10 h). Photoproduct was separated as 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative, recrystallised, m.p. 228° . Separately, same reaction mixture was prepared and diluted in dry acetone medium and the progress was studied spectrophotometrically at 660 nm. After completion of photochemical reaction, the photoproduct was characterized by its usual qualitative tests⁸. Elemental and IR analysis were also performed. The control experiments were performed which concluded that uranyl ions and light are necessary for the reaction and oxygen increases the yield of the product⁹.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. (Mrs.) P. Choudhary and Dr. V. K. Vaidya of Chemistry Department of M. L. V. Govt. P. G. College, Bhilwara, for their valuable suggestions.

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